

Synthesis of some New Benzofuro[2,3-*c*]pyridazin-3(1*H*)-ones and Benzofuro[2,3-*c*]pyrazol-3-ones

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The benzofuran derivatives have exhibited various biological activities¹. The esterogenic activity of some furocoumarins has been extensively recorded². Recently, the synthesis of new benzofuranopyrazoles and benzofuranopyrimidines have been recorded^{3,4}. We report herein some new benzofuranopyridazinones and benzofuranopyrazoles.

Results and Discussion

Thymoxyacetic acid was prepared by the reaction of thymol with chloroacetic acid in presence of alkali⁵ which on bromination gave 4-bromothymoxyacetic acid. Thymoxyacetic acid and 4-bromothymo-

xyacetic acid on polyphosphoric acid cyclisation gave the benzofurone **2** and **2'** respectively. Their formation was evidenced by disappearance of acidic-OH encountered at δ 14.5 in the pmr spectra and broad ir band at 3 100–3 400 cm^{-1} . The conversion of compound **2** to **3** and **2'** to **3'** was confirmed by the appearance of ester carbonyl and furocarbonyl ir bands around 1 740 and 1 720 cm^{-1} respectively. The formation of the substituted benzofuro[2,3-*c*]pyridazin-3(1*H*)-ones (**4** and **4'**) from the esters (**3** and **3'**) respectively and substituted arylhydrazides was confirmed by disappearance of the furocarbonyl and ester carbonyl and the appearance of the amido carbonyl around 1 680 cm^{-1} in

the ir spectra of 4 and 4'. The formation of the substituted-benzofuro[2,3-*c*]pyrazol-3(1*H*)-ones (6) from the ester (5) and substituted arylhydrazides was confirmed by disappearance of the furocar-

bonyl and ester carbonyl and appearance of the amido carbonyl at 1 680 cm^{-1} in the ir spectra. The structures of all the compounds have been supported by spectral analysis.

4a, 4'a, 6a : R = *m*- CH_3 , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_2$
 4b, 4'b, 6b : R = *p*- CH_3 , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_2$
 4c, 4'c, 6c : R = 3- CH_3 -4- Cl , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{OCH}_2$
 4d, 4'd, 6d : R = *p*- NO_2 , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_2$
 4e, 4'e, 6e : R = *o*- Cl , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_2$
 4f, 4'f, 6f : R = 3,5-(NO_2)₂- C_6H_3
 4g, 4'g, 6g : R = *p*- Cl , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}$, CH_3
 4h, 4'h, 6h : R = 2-OH-5- Cl , C_6H_3
 4i, 4'i : R = 2,4-(CH_3)₂, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{OCH}$, CH_3
 4j, 4'j : R = *o*- CH_3 , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}$, CH_3

4k, 4'k : R = *m*- CH_3 , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH-CH}_3$
 4l, 6l : R = *o*- NO_2 , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_2$
 4m : R = 3- CH_3 -4- Cl , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{OCH}$, CH_3
 4n : R = *o*- CH_3 , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_2$
 4o : R = 2,4-(Cl)₂, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{OCH}_2$
 4p : R = $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{OCH}$, CH_3
 4q : R = $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{OCH}_2$
 4r : R = *o*- Cl , C_6H_4
 4'l, 6j : R = 2(CH_3)₂, CH , 5- CH_3 , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{OCH}_2$
 6k : R = $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-CH}_2$

Comps. 4'a-1 and 6a-k are 8- and 7-bromosubstituted derivatives respectively.

Scheme 1

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillary tube and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-237 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CDCl_3/TFA) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as internal reference. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc using silica gel G.

Thymoxyacetic acid was prepared from thymol and chloroacetic acid by a known method⁵ which on bromination gave 4-bromothymoxyacetic acid. Similarly, 4-methyl-7-isopropylbenzofuran-3(2H)-one (2) was prepared by the reported method^{4,5}.

4-Methyl-5-bromo-7-isopropyl benzofuran-3(2H)-one (2'): A mixture of 4-bromothymoxyacetic acid (0.03 mol) in polyphosphoric acid (15 ml) and P_2O_5 (8 g) was stirred for 30 min and heated further gently on a water-bath at 80° for about 2 h, then cooled and poured in ice-water (200 ml). The resulting solid was washed with sodium bicarbonate and recrystallised from alcohol, (58%), m.p. 77° (Found: C, 53.51; H, 4.80. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{Br}$ requires: C, 53.53; H, 4.83%); ν_{max} 1720 (cyclic C=O), 1600 (C=C) and $1035-1050\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (-O-); δ 1.1 (6H, d, J 7 Hz, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 3.18 (1H, m, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 4.6 (2H, s, OCH_2) and 6.8 (1H, s, $\text{C}_6\text{-ArH}$).

4-Methyl-7-isopropyl-2,3-dihydro-3-oxo-benzofuro-2-ethylacetate (3): To a mixture of 2 (0.025 mol) and ethyl chloroacetate (0.05 mol) in acetone (40 ml), K_2CO_3 (5 g) was added and the mixture refluxed for 18 h, then cooled and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (58%), m.p. 103° (Found: C, 69.51; H, 7.23. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 69.56; H, 7.24%); ν_{max} 1740 (ester C=O), 1720 (cyclic C=O), 1580-1600 (C=C) and $1035-1060\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (-O-); δ 1.1 (6H, d, J 7 Hz, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.3 (3H, t, J 8.5 Hz, CH_3 ester), 2.3 (3H, s, $\text{C}_4\text{-ArCH}_3$), 2.6 (2H, d, CH_2CO), 3.2 (1H, m, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 4.2 (2H, q, J 8.5, OCH_2 ester), 4.6 (1H, t, OCH) and 6.8-6.9 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, ArH).

4-Methyl-5-bromo-7-isopropyl-2,3-dihydro-3-oxo-benzofuro-2-ethylacetate (3'): To a mixture of 2' (0.025 mol) and ethyl chloroacetate (0.05 mol) in acetone (40 ml), K_2CO_3 (5 g) was added and the reaction mixture refluxed for 18 h, then cooled and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (62%), m.p. 83° (Found: C, 54.00; H, 5.30. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_4\text{Br}$ requires: C, 54.08; H, 5.53%); ν_{max} 1740 (ester C=O), 1720 (cyclic C=O), 1600 (C=C) and 1060 cm^{-1} (-O-); δ 1.1 (6H, d, J 7 Hz, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.3 (3H, t, J 8.5 Hz, CH_3 ester), 2.3 (3H, s, $\text{C}_4\text{-ArCH}_3$), 2.6 (2H, d, CH_2CO), 3.2 (1H, m, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 4.15 (2H, q, J 8.5 Hz, OCH_2 ester), 4.65 (1H, t, OCH) and 6.8 (1H, s, $\text{C}_6\text{-ArH}$).

2-Aroyl-6-isopropyl-9-methylbenzofuro[2,3-c]pyridazin-3(1H)-one (4a): To a solution 3 (0.005 mol) in methanol (25 ml), *m*-methylphenoxyacetic

acid hydrazide (0.005 mol) was added and the mixture refluxed for 5 h on a water-bath and then the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The separated solid was crystallised from methanol, (49%), m.p. 98° (Found: C, 70.36; H, 6.10; N, 7.12. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires: C, 70.40; H, 6.12; N, 7.14%); ν_{max} 3300-3250 (NH), 1670 (broad -CON-) and 1600 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ 1.1 (6H, d, J 7 Hz, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 2.3 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{ArCH}_3$), 2.45 (2H, s, OCH_2), 3.2, (1H, m, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 4.6 (2H, s, OCH_2) and 6.8-7.3 (6H, m, ArH). Similarly other pyridazinones (yields 51-85%) were prepared: 4b, m.p. 128° ; c, 167° ; d, 135° ; e, 194° ; f, 117° ; g, 127° ; h, 133° ; i, 110° ; j, 82° ; k, 93° ; l, 76° ; m, 125° ; n, 59° ; o, 53° ; p, 72° ; q, 216° ; r, 71° .

2-Aroyl-6-isopropyl-8-bromo-9-methylbenzofuro[2,3-c]pyridazin-3(1H)-one (4'a): To a solution of 3' (0.005 mol) in methanol (25 ml), *m*-methylphenoxyacetic acid hydrazide (0.0005 mol) was added and the reaction mixture refluxed for 4 h on a water-bath. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the separated solid was crystallised from methanol, (50%), m.p. 91° (Found: C, 58.51; H, 4.80; N, 5.91. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_4\text{Br}$ requires: C, 58.59; H, 4.88; N, 5.94%); ν_{max} 3300-3200 (NH), 1680 (-CON-) and 1600 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ 1.1 (6H, d, J 7 Hz, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.3 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{ArCH}_3$), 2.45 (2H, s, COCH_2), 3.2 (1H, m, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 4.6 (2H, s, OCH_2) and 6.8-7.3 (5H, m, ArH). Similarly other pyridazinones (yields 48-77%) were prepared: 4'b, m.p. 76° ; c, 141° ; d, 104° ; e, 153° ; f, 156° ; g, 36° ; h, 213° ; i, 114° ; j, 107° ; k, 83° ; l, 118° .

4-Methyl-5-bromo-7-isopropyl-3-oxobenzofuro-2-ethylcarboxylate (5): To a mixture of (2') (0.025 mol) and ethyl chloroformate (0.05 mol) in acetone (40 ml), K_2CO_3 (5 g) was added and the reaction mixture refluxed for 18 h, then cooled and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The solid formed was crystallised from ethanol, (62%), m.p. 97° (Found: C, 52.70; H, 4.91. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_4\text{Br}$ requires: C, 52.78, H, 4.98%); ν_{max} 1740 (ester C=O), 1720 (cyclic C=O), 1580-1600 (C=C) and $1085-1060\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (-O-); δ 1.1 (6H, d, J 7 Hz, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.3 (3H, t, J 8.5 Hz, ester CH_3), 2.3 (3H, s, $\text{C}_4\text{-ArCH}_3$), 3.2 (1H, m, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 4.2 (2H, q, J 8.5 Hz, OCH_2 -ester), 4.6 (1H, s, -OCH-) and 6.8-6.9 (1H, s, J 8 Hz, ArH).

2-Aroyl-5-isopropyl-7-bromo-8-methylbenzofuro[2,3-c]pyrazol-3-(1H)-one (6a): To a solution of 5 (0.003 mol) in methanol (25 ml), *m*-methylphenoxyacetic acid hydrazide (0.0003 mol) was added and the reaction mixture refluxed for 5 h on a water-bath. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the solid separated was crystallised from methanol, (59%), m.p. 93° (Found: C, 57.61; H, 4.51; N, 6.09. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_4\text{H}_2\text{Br}$ requires: C, 57.76; H, 4.59; N, 6.12%); ν_{max} 3300-3250 (NH), 1690-1600 (C=O) and 1600 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ 1.1 (6H, d, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 2.3 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{ArCH}_3$), 3.2 (1H, m, CH), 4.6 (2H, s, OCH_2) and 6.8-7.3 (5H, m, ArH) Similarly

other pyrazolones (yields 57–87%) were prepared :
6b, 107° ; **c**, 140° ; **d**, 97° ; **e**, 121° ; **f**, 133° ; **g**, 128° ;
h, 185° ; **i** (54%), 110° ; **j**, 118° ; **k**, 162°.

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